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## INSTALL REQUIRED PACKAGES ##
install.packages("NbClust")
install.packages("factoextra")

## RUN PACKAGES ##
library(readxl)
library(NbClust)
library(factoextra)

## READ DATA ##
WNL_TIS <- read_excel("planilha_com_valores_TIS_e_WNL")

## SELECT NUMERIC COLUMNS (E.G. COLUMNS 2 AND 3 WITH VALUES) ##
df <- WNL_TIS[, c(1, 2)]

## STANDARDIZE DATA ##
df_scaled <- scale(df)

## DETERMINE OPTIMAL NUMBER OF CLUSTERS ##
set.seed(123) # for reproducibility
res_nc <- NbClust(data = df_scaled, distance = "euclidean", min.nc = 2, max.nc = 10,
method = "kmeans")

## RUN K-MEANS WITH THE OPTIMAL NUMBER FOUND ##
km <- kmeans(df_scaled, centers = 7, nstart = 25)

## VIEW RESULT ##
print(km)
fviz_cluster(km, data = df_scaled, geom = "point", ellipse.type = "norm")
```